

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**RP-HPLC METHOD FOR SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF
ROSUVASTATIN AND AMLODIPINE IN BULK AND
PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORM**Chavan Dipanjali Kailas¹, S. Shalini², P. Aravindra Reddy³

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Article Received: October 2024 Accepted: November 2024 Published: December 2024**Abstract:**

A variety of methods and approaches are used in analytical chemistry to gather and evaluate qualitative, quantitative, and structural data on the nature of matter. The present communication deals with the development of a new drug, simple, specific, sensitive, rapid and economical procedure for simultaneous estimation of rosuvastatin and amlodipine in a combined dosage form. The method is based on the native ultraviolet absorbance maxima of the two chemotherapeutic agents. Both the drugs obeyed Beer's law in the concentration range that was employed in the method. The UV detector response of rosuvastatin and amlodipine was studied and the best wavelength was found to be 251 nm showing highest sensitivity. Several modifications in the mobile phase composition were made in order to study the possibilities of changing the selectivity of the chromatographic system. All the results were within the limits. The method is very simple, rapid and economic in nature.

Key words: Amlodipine, Rosuvastatin, RP-HPLC, validation.**Corresponding author:****S.Shalini,**Mother Teresa College of Pharmacy,
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Please cite this article in press **S.Shalini et al** *Rp-Hplc Method For Simultaneous Estimation Of Rosuvastatin And Amlodipine In Bulk And Pharmaceutical Dosage Form., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2024; 11 (12).*

INTRODUCTION:

Analytical chemistry is a scientific discipline used to study the chemical composition, structure and behaviour of matter. The purposes of chemical analysis are together and interpret chemical information that will be of value to society in a wide range of contexts. Quality control in manufacturing industries, the monitoring of clinical and environmental samples, the assaying of geological specimens, and the support of fundamental and applied research are the principal applications.

Rosuvastatin is chemically, 7-{{4-(4-Fluorophenyl)-6-isopropyl-2-[methyl(methylsulfonyl)amino]pyrimidin-5-yl}}-3,5-dihydroxyhept-6-enoic acid is a member of the drug class of statins, is a competitive inhibitor of HMG-COA reductase enzyme. It is mainly used for treatment of hypercholesterolemia and prevention of cardiovascular disease. Rosuvastatin acts primarily in the liver. Decreased hepatic cholesterol

concentrations stimulate the upregulation of hepatic low-density lipoprotein (LDL) receptors which increases hepatic uptake of LDL. Rosuvastatin also inhibits hepatic synthesis of very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL). Rosuvastatin calcium is official in Indian Pharmacopoeia and Martindale, the extra Pharmacopoeia.

Amlodipine is chemically designated as 3-ethyl 5-methyl-2-(2-aminoethoxymethyl)-4-(2-chlorophenyl)-1, 4-dihydro-6-methyl-3, 5pyridine dicarboxylate benzene sulphonate. It is the besylate salt of Amlodipine, a long-acting calcium channel blocker used in treatment of hypertension and coronary artery diseases. Amlodipine is a long-acting CCB that may be used to treat mild to moderate essential hypertension and exertion-related angina (chronic stable angina). Amlodipine besylate is official in Indian pharmacopoeia, Martindale, The extra pharmacopoeia, European pharmacopoeia and United states pharmacopoeia.

Figure 1: Chemical structure of rosuvastatin

Figure 2: Chemical structure of amlodipine

MATERIALS AND METHODS:**Instrumentation:**

Instrumentation and Chromatographic Conditions: The HPLC system consisted of a binary pump (model Waters 515 HPLC pump), auto sampler (model 717 plus Auto sampler), column heater and PDA detector. Data collection and analysis were performed using Empower - version 2 software. Separation was

achieved on Aquasil C₁₈ column (150 mm × 4.6 mm, 5.0 μm) column maintained at 50°C using column oven. Isocratic elution with acetonitrile: THF: water pH 3 (68:12:20 % v/v) mobile phase at the flow rate of 0.5 ml/min was carried out. The detection was monitored at 251 nm and injection volume was 10 μl. The peak purity was checked with the PDA.

Table 1: Optimized chromatographic conditions

Instrument used	Waters HPLC with auto sampler and PDA detector 996 model
Temperature	Ambient
Column	Aquasil C ₁₈ (4.6×150mm, 5.0 μm)
Buffer	Phosphate buffer (pH 3.8)-Dissolve 0.9g of anhydrous dihydrogen phosphate and 1.298 g of citric acid monohydrate in sufficient water to produce 1000mL. Adjust the pH 3.8 by using ortho phosphoric acid.
pH	3.8
Mobile phase	ACN: Phosphate buffer (pH3.8), Methanol in proportion 30:60:10 v/v respectively.
Flow rate	1 ml/min
Wavelength	251 nm
Injection volume	20 μl
Run time	8 min

Preparation of mobile phase:

Accurately measured 300 ml (30%) of HPLC Acetonitrile, 600 ml of Phosphate buffer(3.8) (60%) and 100 ml HPLC Methanol (10%) were mixed and degassed in a digital ultrasonicator for 10 min and then filtered through 0.45 μ filter under vacuum filtration.

Diluent preparation: The Mobile phase was used as the diluent.

Validation parameters:**Linearity:**

Accurately weigh 10 combination tablets crush in mortar and pestle and transfer equivalent to 10 mg equivalent weight of Rosuvastatin (marketed formulation-dose of Amlodipine is 5 mg, Dose of Rosuvastatin is 10 mg in combination tablet) sample into a 10mL clean dry volumetric flask add about 10

mL of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution-1000ppm). Further pipette 1 ml of above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent. (Stock solution-100 ppm).

Accuracy:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Rosuvastatin and 10mg of Amlodipine working standard into a 10 mL and 10 ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 10mL and 10 ml of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution) Further pipette 0.15 ml and 0.075 ml of the above Rosuvastatin, Amlodipine stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**System suitability:****Figure 3: Chromatogram for system suitability**

Linearity:**Figure 5: Calibration curve of****Assay:**

The % purity of rosuvastatin and amlodipine pharmaceutical dosage form was found to be 99% and 98% respectively.

Table 2: Assay

S. No.	Drug	Label claim (mg)	Amount found (mg)	%Assay
1	Rosuvastatin	10	9.9	99%
2	Amlodipine	5	4.9	98%

Accuracy:

Three different quantities (low, medium and high) of the authentic standards were added to the placebo. The resulting sample solutions were injected and chromatograms were recorded. The mean percentage recoveries obtained for ROSUVASTATIN AND AMLODIPINE were 99.55 % and 99.67 %, respectively.

Table 3: Accuracy of rosuvastatin and amlodipine

Compound	Recovery Level (%)	Qty. spiked ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Qty. recovered ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	% Recovery	% RSD
Rosuvastatin	50	25	24.64	98.56	0.52
	100	50	49.27	101.48	0.84
	150	75	74.53	100.63	0.32
Amlodipine	50	12.5	12.29	101.70	0.76
	100	25	25.32	98.73	0.49
	150	37.5	37.81	99.18	0.81

Linear, precise, and accurate RP-HPLC-PDA method has been developed and validated for quantitative determination of rosuvastatin and amlodipine from tablet formulations. All the parameters for the two titled drugs met the criteria of ICH guidelines for method validation.

CONCLUSION:

High performance liquid chromatography is at present one of the most sophisticated tools of the analysis. The estimation of rosuvastatin and amlodipine was done by RP-HPLC. The Phosphate buffer was pH 6 and the mobile phase was optimized with consists of methanol: Phosphate buffer (pH-6) mixed in the ratio of 65:35 % v/v. A Symmetry C₁₈ column C₁₈ (4.6 x 150mm, 5 μm) or equivalent chemically bonded to porous silica particles was used as stationary phase. The solutions were chromatographed at a constant flow rate of 1 ml/min. the linearity range of Rosuvastatin and Amlodipine were found to be from 32-160 ppm, 20-100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively. Linear regression coefficient was not more than 0.999, 0.999.

The values of % RSD are less than 2% indicating accuracy and precision of the method. The percentage recovery varies from 100.0 -100.3% of Rosuvastatin and Amlodipine LOD and LOQ were found to be within limit. The results obtained on the validation parameters met ICH and USP requirements .it inferred the method found to be simple, accurate, precise and linear. The method was found to be having suitable application in routine laboratory analysis with high degree of accuracy and precision.

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